

STUDIES on CHEMOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY of NEOCHLOROGENIC ACID and EPIGALLOCATECHIN GALLATE on DIBUTYLTIN DICHLORIDE INDUCED PANCREATIC CANCER in WISTAR RATS

Archan Kumar Mamillapalli*, Eswar Kumar Kilari

A.U. College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Andhra university, Visakhapatnam, AP, India.

*Corresponding Author: Archan Kumar Mamillapalli

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Abstract:

This study investigated the protective effects of Neochlorogenic Acid (NA) and Epigallocatechin Gallate (EGCG) against pancreatic cancer induced by Dibutyltin Dichloride (DBTC) in Wistar rats. The animals were divided into six groups, with the first serving as a control. Groups 2–6 received DBTC injections intraperitoneally once prior to treatment. In addition, groups 3 and 4 were treated with NA at doses of 10 mg/kg and 20 mg/kg PO, respectively, while groups 5 and 6 received EGCG at doses of 10 mg/kg and 20 mg/kg PO, respectively throughout the experimental period. After 28 days of treatment, the rats were sacrificed for biochemical analysis. Treatment with NA and EGCG resulted in normalized hematological profiles, decreased liver enzymes (SGOT, SGPT, ALP, GGT), reduced LDH, bilirubin, digestive enzymes (amylase, lipase), and glucose levels. Antioxidant enzyme activities (SOD, CAT, GR, GSH) were significantly elevated, while markers of oxidative stress (MDA, PCC) were reduced. Additionally, pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF- α and IL-6 decreased, whereas anti-inflammatory IL-10 increased. These results suggest that NA and EGCG exert chemopreventive effects against DBTC-induced pancreatic cancer by modulating oxidative stress, enhancing antioxidant defence, and reducing inflammatory responses, thereby preventing histopathological damage.

Key words: DBTC, Pancreatic cancer, Neochlorogenic Acid, Epigallocatechin Gallate and Wistar rat

I. INTRODUCTION

Pancreatic cancer is a highly aggressive malignancy with a global impact. It is classified into three main types, with pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) being the most prevalent, originating from the ductal cells of the exocrine pancreas and accounting for over 90% of cases. A less common variant, adenosquamous carcinoma, exhibits features of both adenocarcinoma and squamous carcinoma and represents about 1–4% of cases. Other rare forms include acinar and neuroendocrine tumors. According to GLOBOCAN 2020 data, approximately 495,773 new pancreatic cancer cases and 466,000 related deaths were reported worldwide. Early detection remains challenging because the disease often progresses silently without noticeable symptoms. When present, symptoms may include abdominal or back pain, weight loss, indigestion, poor appetite, jaundice, diarrhoea, constipation, blood clots, and fatigue. Although these manifestations are nonspecific and may arise from other causes, prompt medical evaluation is essential if they occur (Simone CG et al., 2013; Ilic I et al., 2022).

Several drugs have been approved for the treatment of pancreatic cancer, including Fluorouracil (5-FU), Capecitabine, Gemcitabine, Erlotinib, Leucovorin, Irinotecan, Nab-paclitaxel, nanoliposomal irinotecan, and Oxaliplatin. In addition to these, targeted therapies have been developed to act on specific genes, proteins, or tumor microenvironments. For example, Erlotinib targets the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), Olaparib is effective against hereditary BRCA mutations, and Larotrectinib is used to treat cancers with NTRK gene fusions (Filippi et al., 2021; Tutt et al., 2021).

Several plant-derived anticancer agents are currently used to treat a wide range of cancers, such as breast, stomach, prostate, ovarian, lung, brain, bladder, and thyroid cancers, as well as Hodgkin's and non-Hodgkin's lymphomas, melanoma, leukaemia, neuroblastoma, multiple myeloma, and chronic myeloid leukaemia. Examples of these include docetaxel, paclitaxel, vinblastine, camptothecin, vincristine, and homoharringtonine. Notably, approximately 60% of the chemotherapeutic drugs used to treat pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) are derived from plants, with paclitaxel being one of the most commonly used agents (Joshi PR., 2020). Furthermore, plant-derived compounds and their phytochemicals have demonstrated the ability to enhance drug sensitivity and overcome resistance during therapy. Consequently, there is increasing interest in exploring these natural products as promising candidates for PDAC management. This study aims to emphasize the role of plant-derived products and phytochemicals in addressing PDAC and to contribute toward developing sustainable therapeutic strategies against this challenging disease.

II. MATERIALS and METHODS

The experiment was carried out using healthy adult Wistar rats of either sex, aged 8–12 weeks, obtained from Mahaveer Enterprises, Hyderabad. All experimental procedures complied with the guidelines of the Committee for the Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA) and were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee. The rats were monitored continuously throughout the study period. Neochlorogenic Acid (W228826) and Epigallocatechin Gallate (09582) were procured from Merck.

A. Tumour Induction

Dibutyltin dichloride was prepared by dissolving it in 96% ethanol (2 parts) and mixing with glycerol (3 parts) to induce acute pancreatitis. Rats received an intraperitoneal injection of DBTC at a dose of 6 mg/kg body weight (Merkord et al., 2001). The animals were divided into six groups, with the first group serving as the control. Groups 2–6 were administered DBTC (ip) once prior to treatment. In addition, groups 3 and 4 received neochlorogenic acid (NA) at doses of 10 mg/kg and 20 mg/kg PO, respectively, while groups 5 and 6 were treated with epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) at the same doses orally throughout the experimental period. After 28 days, the rats were sacrificed, and blood parameters along with liver enzyme levels were analyzed.

B. Blood / Serum samples

After completing the 28-day dosing period, blood samples were collected from all animals on the 29th day through retro-orbital plexus puncture under light ether anaesthesia using a capillary tube. Samples collected in K3EDTA tubes were used for hematological analysis, while those collected in plain centrifuge tubes (without anticoagulant) were left to clot at room temperature ($26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). The serum was then separated by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, stored at -40°C for biochemical analysis, and analyzed within 12 hours.

C. Collection of Tissues

After blood sample collection on day 29, all rats were euthanized by cervical dislocation. A complete post-mortem examination was conducted on each animal to assess the presence or absence of any gross or histopathological lesions. All observed lesions were carefully documented, and tissue samples from the pancreas and liver were collected and preserved in 10% formalin for histopathological analysis.

D. Biochemical Assessments

Complete blood counts were analyzed using an automated haematology analyzer. Liver and digestive enzymes, along with glucose levels, were measured using semi-autoanalyzer kits. Lipid peroxidation was assessed by determining thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) following with absorbance recorded at 532 nm Ohkawa et al. (1979). Reduced glutathione (GSH) levels were estimated using the Ellman method (1959), based on the reaction of DTNB with sulfhydryl groups, and expressed as μmoles of GSH utilized per minute per milligram of protein. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity was determined by the method of Kakkar et al. (1984), measuring 50% inhibition of NBT reduction at 520 nm. Catalase activity was assayed following Sinha (1972) by measuring chromic acetate formation at 590 nm, and expressed as μmoles of H_2O_2 decomposed per minute per milligram of protein. Levels of TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-10 were quantified using ELISA kits.

E. Histopathology

A portion of the tissue was promptly fixed in 10% formalin for 24 hours. It was then opened along the antimesenteric border, embedded in paraffin wax, sectioned into 3–5 μm slices, and stained with haematoxylin and eosin. The overall cellular morphology was examined using standard histological procedures (Carson, 1990).

III. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

In this study, DBTC was used as an effective experimental model to induce progressive interstitial pancreatitis, which gradually develops chronic characteristics similar to human pancreatic disease. The pathogenesis is initiated by necrosis of the epithelial lining of the common bile duct. The detached epithelial debris forms plugs in the distal bile duct, leading to severe extrahepatic cholestasis. Consequently, this causes peribiliary liver inflammation and elevated plasma levels of alkaline phosphatase and bilirubin (Merkord et al., 2001). In the present investigation, DBTC-induced pancreatic cancer was associated with interstitial pancreatitis and bile duct injury.

A complete blood count (CBC) assesses red blood cells, white blood cells, and platelets. Chemotherapy or radiation exposure can markedly decrease these cells, heightening infection risk (Younis, 2015). Among these parameters, the lymphocyte count serves as an indicator of cellular immune response in cancer patients, while variations in hematological values can affect disease progression. Low haemoglobin (Hb) and packed cell volume (PCV) levels are correlated with fatigue, bleeding, and an increased likelihood of cardiac failure. Elevated total leukocyte count (TLC) generally indicates poor prognosis, whereas total and differential white blood cell counts and platelet counts help evaluate disease severity and mortality risk.

The mean corpuscular volume (MCV) measures the average size and volume of red blood cells and aids in diagnosing anaemia. It is calculated by multiplying the haematocrit percentage by ten and dividing by the erythrocyte count. Increased MCV is influenced by factors such as aging, nutritional status, and alcohol consumption, and it also serves as a survival predictor in chronic illnesses (Maner, 2023). A high MCV reflects enlarged red blood cells and may signal underlying myelodysplastic syndromes—cancers of the bone marrow.

In DBTC-induced pancreatic cancer, CBC parameters were notably altered, with reduced Hb (8.38 ± 0.23), total erythrocyte count (TEC) (6.98 ± 0.14), and PCV (38.12 ± 0.25), alongside elevated TLC (9.74 ± 0.38), MCV (62.18 ± 0.76), and MCHC (37.77 ± 0.18). Treatment with neochlorogenic acid (NA) and epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) at varying doses significantly restored these hematological parameters toward normal levels, as presented in Table I & II.

TABLE I: EFFECT OF NA and EGCG on HEMATOLOGICAL PARAMETERS in DBTC-INDUCED PANCREATIC CANCER

Groups/ Parameter	Hb (g/dL)	TLC ($10^9/L$)	TEC ($10^{12}/L$)
Vehicle Control	$12.54 \pm 0.25^{***}$	$7.86 \pm 0.18^{***}$	$9.37 \pm 0.14^{***}$
DBTC Control	8.38 ± 0.23	9.74 ± 0.38	6.98 ± 0.14
NA (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$8.52 \pm 0.32^*$	$8.89 \pm 0.35^{**}$	$7.52 \pm 0.15^{**}$
NA (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$10.24 \pm 0.18^{***}$	$8.05 \pm 0.18^{***}$	$8.16 \pm 0.06^{***}$
EGCG (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$9.37 \pm 0.36^{***}$	$8.32 \pm 0.18^{***}$	$7.95 \pm 0.07^{***}$
EGCG (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$11.37 \pm 0.65^{***}$	$7.85 \pm 0.31^{***}$	$8.88 \pm 0.15^{***}$

TABLE II: EFFECT OF NA AND EGCG on HAEMATOLOGICAL PARAMETERS in DBTC-INDUCED PANCREATIC CANCER

Groups/ Parameter	MCV (fL)	MCHC (g/dL)	PCV (%)
Vehicle Control	$56.34 \pm 0.27^{**}$	$34.30 \pm 0.12^{***}$	$42.42 \pm 0.18^{***}$
DBTC Control	62.18 ± 0.76	37.77 ± 0.18	38.12 ± 0.25
NA (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$60.15 \pm 0.05^{**}$	$35.45 \pm 0.30^{**}$	$40.44 \pm 0.56^{***}$
NA (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$57.62 \pm 0.42^{***}$	$33.12 \pm 0.27^{**}$	$41.05 \pm 0.12^{***}$
EGCG (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$58.85 \pm 0.60^{***}$	$35.16 \pm 0.24^{***}$	$41.16 \pm 0.44^{***}$
EGCG (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$56.82 \pm 0.55^{***}$	$33.52 \pm 0.46^{**}$	$42.45 \pm 0.25^{***}$

Hb: Hemoglobin; TLC: Total Leukocyte Count; TEC: Total Erythrocyte Count; MCV: Mean Corpuscular Volume; MCHC: Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration; PCV: Packed Cell Volume. All values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM. Statistical comparisons were made by using One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test using Graph Pad Prism version 8 and found significant at $p > 0.05^{ns}$, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$ when compared to disease control

Neochlorogenic Acid (NA) exhibits multiple mechanisms of action, including the regulation of glucose and lipid metabolism by mitigating oxidative stress and inflammation-induced insulin resistance. It also downregulates the expression of lipogenic and gluconeogenic genes while enhancing insulin signaling (Singdam P., 2023). In HepG2 cells, NA treatment markedly reduced oleic acid (OA)-induced lipid accumulation, and in db/db mice, it lowered triglyceride (TG) levels in a dose-dependent manner. In rats with gentamycin-induced hepatic dysfunction, NA administration significantly decreased serum AST, ALT, and ALP levels, while alleviating oxidative stress by reducing MDA and oxide content and increasing antioxidant enzymes such as CAT and GPX (Esmael B., 2021).

Synchronous liver metastasis refers to liver metastases identified at the initial diagnosis of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC), whereas metachronous metastasis appears later during follow-up imaging, irrespective of the time elapsed since diagnosis. Elevated AST, ALT, and CA19-9 levels are associated with a higher risk of synchronous liver metastasis in PDAC patients (Hatwell C., 2004). The AST/ALT ratio serves as a negative prognostic indicator in PDAC. Clinicians routinely assess liver enzymes and bilirubin to monitor hepatic function in pancreatic cancer patients, as elevated bilirubin is a frequent finding. Increased ALP levels may also occur in patients with solid pancreatic tumors, particularly following surgical resection, and can indicate lymph node involvement and a greater likelihood of rapid recurrence and disease progression (Xiao Y., 2019).

In experimental models, DBTC induction led to marked hepatic injury, reflected by elevated serum enzyme levels AST (124.55 ± 2.82), ALT (67.37 ± 1.56), and ALP (235.25 ± 3.77). However, treatment with NA and EGCG significantly reduced these enzyme levels, demonstrating hepatoprotective effects (see Table III)

TABLE III: EFFECT OF NA AND EGCG on LIVER BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS in DBTC-INDUCED PANCREATIC CANCER

Groups/ Parameter	AST (IU/dL)	ALT (IU/dL)	ALP (IU/dL)
Vehicle Control	$75.32 \pm 2.15^{***}$	$42.46 \pm 2.64^{***}$	$172.05 \pm 5.07^{***}$
DBTC Control	124.55 ± 2.82	67.37 ± 1.56	235.25 ± 3.77
NA (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$98.30 \pm 3.44^{***}$	$57.30 \pm 1.18^{***}$	$205.12 \pm 2.28^{***}$
NA (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$90.27 \pm 3.18^{***}$	$51.33 \pm 1.22^{***}$	$192.51 \pm 2.60^{***}$
EGCG (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$94.61 \pm 2.85^{***}$	$53.15 \pm 2.60^{***}$	$197.14 \pm 4.05^{***}$
EGCG (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$83.18 \pm 1.74^{***}$	$44.28 \pm 3.14^{***}$	$178.55 \pm 3.42^{***}$

AST: Aspartate Aminotransferase; ALT: Alanine Aminotransferase; ALP: Alkaline Phosphate. All values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM. Statistical comparisons were made by using One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test using Graph Pad Prism version 8 and found significant at $p > 0.05^{ns}$, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$ when compared to disease control

Elevated gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) levels have been associated with reduced survival in patients with unresectable PDAC. Inflammation-related oxidative stress and cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha are known to elevate serum GGT levels (Luo C., 2017). Moreover, GGT itself may promote cancer progression and metastasis; studies on melanoma cells have demonstrated that increased GGT activity confers growth advantages both *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Wang Q., 2017).

Lactate dehydrogenase A (LDHA), a key enzyme in the final step of aerobic glycolysis, is also implicated in tumor development. Overexpression of LDHA enhances pancreatic cancer cell proliferation, whereas its downregulation markedly suppresses cell growth (Yu SL., 2017). High serum LDH levels in cancer patients are correlated with metastasis and poor prognosis, with elevated LDH concentrations linked to reduced survival in several solid tumors, including gastrointestinal and lung cancers.

In the present study, treatment with NA and EGCG significantly reduced LDH (374.25 ± 4.32 and 368.05 ± 4.44), GGT (3.30 ± 0.14 and 2.86 ± 0.12), and bilirubin (0.42 ± 0.02 and 0.39 ± 0.05) levels, respectively, in DBTC-induced pancreatic cancer rats (Table IV).

TABLE IV: EFFECT of NA AND EGCG on BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS in DBTC-INDUCED PANCREATIC CANCER

Groups/ Parameter	GGT (IU/mL)	LDH (mU/mL)	Bilirubin (IU/dL)
Vehicle Control	2.42±0.15***	355.34±4.08***	0.38±0.05***
DBTC Control	5.18±0.17	436.24±6.15	0.55±0.04
NA (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	3.87±0.12***	408.55±5.52***	0.45±0.04**
NA (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	3.30±0.14***	374.25±4.32***	0.42±0.02***
EGCG (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	3.55±0.16***	391.27±3.57***	0.50±0.03***
EGCG (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	2.86±0.12***	368.05±4.44***	0.39±0.05***

GGT: Gamma-Glutamyl Transferase; LDH: Lactate Dehydrogenase. All values are expressed as Mean±SEM. Statistical comparisons were made by using One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test using Graph Pad Prism version 8 and found significant at $p>0.05^{ns}$, $*p<0.05$, $**p<0.01$, $***p<0.001$ when compared to disease control

Pancreatic amylase is essential for carbohydrate digestion, breaking complex carbohydrates into glucose a key energy source for the body. Similarly, pancreatic lipase facilitates fat digestion by converting fat globules into fatty acids and glycerol, energy-rich molecules that are transported through the blood and lymphatic systems for cellular use (Yener Y., 2013). In some cases, diabetes is the earliest sign of pancreatic cancer, with nearly one in four patients developing diabetes within six to thirty-six months before cancer diagnosis (Aggarwal G., 2012). Elevated blood glucose levels resulting from insulin resistance and reduced hepatic glucose regulation can promote tumor growth by enhancing epithelial-mesenchymal transition, cancer stem cell traits, and metastatic potential in pancreatic cancer (Jian Z., 2018). Inducing agents such as DBTC target both the exocrine and endocrine regions of the pancreas. However, treatment with NA and EGCG demonstrated a protective effect in rats with DBTC-induced pancreatic cancer, as indicated by reduced serum levels of amylase (2416.18 ± 56.24 and 2346.22 ± 74.04), lipase (56.34 ± 4.14 and 52.35 ± 3.80), and glucose (96.34 ± 5.20 and 91.66 ± 4.18), as shown in Table V.

TABLE V: EFFECT of NA AND EGCG on SERUM BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS in DBTC-INDUCED PANCREATIC CANCER

Groups/ Parameter	Amylase (U/L)	Lipase (U/L)	Glucose (g/dL)
Vehicle Control	2345.75±65.14***	48.42±3.56***	88.12±4.18***
DBTC Control	2547.18±56.05	75.62±5.14	123.56±6.28
NA (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	2478.23±48.35*	65.55±2.05***	114.35±4.50***
NA (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	2416.18±56.24***	56.34±4.14***	96.34±5.20***
EGCG (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	2405.51±62.40***	57.24±3.35***	98.35±5.37***
EGCG (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	2346.22±74.04***	52.35±3.80***	91.66±4.18***

All values are expressed as Mean±SEM. Statistical comparisons were made by using One way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test using Graph Pad Prism version 8 and found significant at $p>0.05^{ns}$, $*p<0.05$, $**p<0.01$, $***p<0.001$ when compared to disease control

According to Modak D. (2021), docking studies revealed that n-Hexadecanoic acid exhibits strong inhibitory effects on cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α), and interleukin-6 (IL-6). Hexadecanoic acid, found in Lupin species, possesses antioxidant properties, maintaining superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) levels while reducing lipid peroxidation (LPO) and malondialdehyde (MDA) in CCl₄-intoxicated rats (Mazumder K., 2020). Bharath B. (2021) reported that

n-Hexadecanoic acid induces apoptosis in 77.83% of cells and inhibits cell progression in the G0/G1 phase, as indicated by increased fluorescence intensity and cell cycle analysis.

In pancreatic tissue, damage to acinar cells and activation of immune cells lead to excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), causing elevated MDA and reduced SOD and total glutathione (GSH) levels. Antioxidant treatment has been shown to decrease acinar cell necrosis and mitigate pancreatic injury (Zhao J., 2014). Oxidative stress-induced protein carbonylation can impair protein function, disrupt cellular redox balance, interfere with the cell cycle, and promote cancer progression, with higher protein carbonylation levels observed in various cancers (Nathan FM., 2011). Supplementation with antioxidants such as N and EGCG supports the antioxidant defence system, significantly increasing pancreatic SOD (2.08 ± 0.05 and 2.14 ± 0.10), CAT (0.74 ± 0.12 and 0.87 ± 0.12), and glutathione reductase (GR) (5.20 ± 0.10 and 5.87 ± 0.16) levels, as presented in Table VI & VII.

TABLE VI: EFFECT of NA AND EGCG on TISSUE BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS in DBTC-INDUCED PANCREATIC CANCER

Groups/ Parameter	SOD (IU/mg of Protein)	CAT (IU/min/mg of Protein)	GR (μmol of NADPH oxidized/min/mg of Protein)
Vehicle Control	$2.46 \pm 0.05^{***}$	$0.92 \pm 0.12^{***}$	$6.25 \pm 0.84^{***}$
DBTC Control	1.56 ± 0.05	0.57 ± 0.03	4.25 ± 0.12
NA (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$1.88 \pm 0.04^*$	$0.62 \pm 0.06^{**}$	$4.56 \pm 0.05^*$
NA (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$2.08 \pm 0.05^{***}$	$0.74 \pm 0.12^{***}$	$5.20 \pm 0.10^{***}$
EGCG (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$1.92 \pm 0.07^{***}$	$0.71 \pm 0.08^{***}$	$5.25 \pm 0.14^{***}$
EGCG (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$2.14 \pm 0.10^{***}$	$0.87 \pm 0.12^{***}$	$5.87 \pm 0.16^{***}$

TABLE VII: EFFECT of NA AND EGCG on TISSUE BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS in DBTC-INDUCED PANCREATIC CANCER

Groups/ Parameter	GSH (nmol/mg of Protein)	PCC (nmol/mg of Protein)	MDA (nmol/mg of Protein)
Vehicle Control	$22.58 \pm 2.36^{***}$	$3.72 \pm 0.24^{***}$	$2.86 \pm 0.76^{***}$
DBTC Control	14.27 ± 0.86	5.68 ± 0.15	7.25 ± 0.52
NA (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$17.35 \pm 1.34^{***}$	$4.35 \pm 0.24^{**}$	$6.17 \pm 0.57^*$
NA (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$19.34 \pm 0.75^{***}$	$4.05 \pm 0.52^{***}$	$5.62 \pm 0.38^{***}$
EGCG (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$19.44 \pm 1.28^{***}$	$4.18 \pm 0.35^{***}$	$5.88 \pm 0.66^{***}$
EGCG (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$21.25 \pm 1.12^{***}$	$3.32 \pm 0.42^{***}$	$3.55 \pm 0.92^{***}$

All values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM. Statistical comparisons were made by using One way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test using Graph Pad Prism version 8 and found significant at $p > 0.05^{ns}$, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$ when compared to disease control

Both systemic and local chronic inflammation can elevate the risk of developing pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC). Inflammatory cells within the tumor microenvironment further promote PDAC progression and metastasis. Inflammation is intricately linked with the immune system, as many of the same immune cells mediate both processes. Recent research indicates that alterations in interleukin expression may serve as markers of poor prognosis in advanced pancreatic cancer (Chari ST). Notably, tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) have been associated with increased cancer risk, tumor growth, and cancer-related cachexia (Porta C). Cytokines, secreted by both tumor and inflammatory cells, are central to this inflammatory and immunomodulatory environment. Key examples include pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF α , the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10, and transforming growth factor-beta (TGF β), which can exert either pro- or anti-tumor effects depending on the context. Treatment interventions effectively reduced pancreatic TNF α (22.42 ± 0.15 and 18.75 ± 0.30) and IL-6 (33.64 ± 0.55 and 30.46 ± 0.75) levels while increasing IL-10 levels (105.32 ± 1.05 and 115.38 ± 4.30) in pancreatic homogenates, as presented in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII: EFFECT of NA AND EGCG on TISSUE BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS in DBTC-INDUCED PANCREATIC CANCER

Groups/ Parameter	TNF alpha (pg/mg of protein)	IL6 (pg/mg of protein)	IL10 (pg/mg of protein)
Vehicle Control	$18.35 \pm 1.25^{***}$	$29.58 \pm 1.25^{***}$	$125.35 \pm 3.15^{***}$
DBTC Control	30.28 ± 0.76	38.46 ± 0.85	82.16 ± 1.88
NA (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$26.12 \pm 0.54^{***}$	$35.64 \pm 0.77^{***}$	$95.62 \pm 2.84^{***}$
NA (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$22.42 \pm 0.15^{***}$	$33.64 \pm 0.55^{***}$	$105.32 \pm 1.05^{***}$
EGCG (10mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$24.56 \pm 0.28^{***}$	$34.38 \pm 0.35^{***}$	$94.36 \pm 1.52^{***}$
EGCG (20mg/kg) bd. Wt + DBTC	$18.75 \pm 0.30^{***}$	$30.46 \pm 0.75^{***}$	$115.38 \pm 4.30^{***}$

All values are expressed as Mean±SEM. Statistical comparisons were made by using One way ANOVA followed by Dunnett’s multiple comparison test using Graph Pad Prism version 8 and found significant at $p > 0.05^ns$, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$ when compared to disease control

Fig. 1 Effect of NA and EGCG on TNF alpha (pg/mg) levels in DBTC induced pancreatic cancer

Fig. 2 Effect of NA and EGCG on IL-6 (pg/mg) levels in DBTC induced pancreatic cancer

Fig. 3 Effect of NA and EGCG on IL-10 (pg/mg) levels in DBTC induced pancreatic cancer

Inflammation can trigger cellular reprogramming, resulting in acinar-to-ductal metaplasia (ADM), a reversible process in which pancreatic acinar cells adopt ductal cell characteristics. This transformation usually occurs in response to pancreatic injury and is considered a potential precursor to pancreatic cancer. While acinar cells produce and secrete digestive enzymes, ductal cells transport these enzymes to the small intestine. DBTC induction promotes oxidative stress and inflammation in the pancreas, as evidenced by histological changes, including damaged acini, alterations in intra- and interlobular ducts, and affected pancreatic islets. Pancreatic cancer often metastasizes to the liver, and similar observations were noted in this study, showing partial liver damage characterized by necrosis, binucleated cells, and disruption of the portal triad. Treatment with neochlorogenic acid (NA) and epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) led to notable, dose-dependent degeneration in both the pancreas and liver, as illustrated in Fig 4 and 5.

Fig. 4 Histopathology of pancreas in animals treated with NA and EGCG in DBTC induced pancreatic cancer

Fig. 5 Histopathology of liver in animals treated with NA and EGCG in DBTC induced pancreatic cancer

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Dibutyltin dichloride (DBTC) effectively induced progressive interstitial pancreatitis and pancreatic cancer in rats, characterized by bile duct epithelial necrosis, cholestasis, peribiliary inflammation, and hepatic injury. DBTC treatment significantly altered hematological parameters (reduced Hb, TEC, PCV; increased TLC, MCV, MCHC), elevated liver enzymes (SGOT, SGPT, ALP, GGT, LDH, bilirubin), disrupted pancreatic exocrine function (amylase, lipase), impaired glucose regulation, and increased oxidative stress (MDA, PCC) while decreasing antioxidants (SOD, CAT, GSH, GR).

Administration of NA and EGCG restored hematological and biochemical parameters, reduced oxidative stress, and improved antioxidant defence. These treatments also modulated inflammatory responses, lowering pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF- α and IL-6 while increasing anti-inflammatory IL-10, and mitigated histopathological damage in both pancreas and liver.

Overall, NA and EGCG demonstrated potent hematological, hepatoprotective, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer effects in DBTC-induced pancreatic cancer, suggesting their therapeutic potential in pancreatic injury and tumor progression. Further studies with specific pancreatic cancer biomarkers are warranted to elucidate underlying mechanisms.

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